

HANDBOOK AND GUIDANCE MATERIAL

FOR IMPLEMENTATION
OF THE MODULAR
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR
AND YOUTH SPORT COACH
EDUCATION AND TRAINING
PROGRAMME

TECHNICAL SHEET

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

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1. INTRODUCTION

This “Handbook and Guidance Material for the Implementation of the modular Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education and Training programme” was developed as part of the multi-year project “Education for Physical Activity and Sport: Informal and non-formal settings” (EduPASS). As part of the EduPASS project, six core modules for Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and for Youth Sport Coaches (YSC) were developed. Implementation in educational settings will help to prepare coaches and educators to deliver high quality physical activity, movement, play and sport (PAMPS) for children and young people non-formal (kindergarten, after-school programs) and in informal (sport clubs).

This handbook and guidance material is designed to enable easy and flexible implementation of the content available in the **EduPASS Online Teaching Platform** in various settings, e.g., in different countries, educational settings or at different educational levels. Within the EduPASS project, this document represents Intellectual Output #8 (IO#8).

The target groups addressed by the handbook and guidance material are the following:

- Early Childhood Educator Institutions and Youth Sport Coach Education Organizations;
- Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches;
- Researchers active in the field of Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education;
- NGOs like research associations, educator, coach or sport associations, etc.;
- Stakeholders and policy makers in charge of Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach Education

The handbook and the guidance material initially provide a classification and explanation of what the EduPASS project is and what its objectives are. The intellectual outputs that have already been realized are briefly presented to provide the users with contextual knowledge. The competence profiles for ECE and YSC are presented first, along with a few reflection questions to support easier implementation in the users’ own organizational and educational context in their own country. Examples of EduPASS-informed Practice from Spain and Luxembourg discuss and demonstrate the added value of the competence-oriented approach of the EduPASS profiles in specific applied settings. Subsequently, the six core modules for each professional profile (ECE and YSC) are presented. Again, a number of reflection questions are presented, to help readers gauge the added benefit the EduPASS results might provide in their respective setting. Additionally, two Examples of EduPASS-informed Practice from EduPASS partner countries are presented, to help readers align their own educational programmes, contexts and organization with the EduPASS results. We believe this approach offers readers an opportunity to transfer the EduPASS content more easily into their own context. Finally, the EduPASS evaluation tool is presented, which is reflected upon and discussed using a further Example of EduPASS-informed practice. Finally, in the Appendix, readers will find a **Self-Check Tool**, which is intended to provide additional support for expanding and adapting one’s own educational programmes.

The mission of EduPASS is to develop an Online Teaching Platform that includes a modular educational programme for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches, and in doing so fostering the delivery of quality physical activity, movement, play and sport (PAMPS) in non-formal and informal settings by strengthening the ECE and YSC professions.

However, it should be highlighted:

A key point to consider for stakeholders in YSC and ECE training and development is that the EduPASS Online Teaching Platform is intended primarily as a resource that provides competency-based training modules that were identified and developed within a comprehensive theoretical and methodological approach. With that said, while the modules can be used by a stakeholder as written, **the EduPASS modular programme is not necessarily intended to be seen/used as a complete, stand-alone YSC/ECE development curriculum.**

As most stakeholders accessing the EduPASS Online Teaching Platform and reading this handbook may already have some form of training programme in place, we think the added value for interested stakeholders lies more in a process of evaluating what they already deliver against what we have created and consider:

- Where can they improve content they already deliver, based on our suggested materials?
- Where do they already have content we highlight well covered?
- Where do they have gaps and should consider adding certain modules/courses/teaching units to improve their YSC/ECE education and training programmes?

With this main objective in mind, the following handbook has been developed as guidance material to facilitate this process.

2. WHAT IS EduPASS?

The EduPASS project aims to promote high-quality non-formal and informal sports and exercise programmes by strengthening the professions of Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and Youth Sport Coaches (YSC). Professionals in these fields play a crucial role in promoting an active lifestyle among children and young people through PAMPS activities.

A central element of the project was the networking of European higher education institutions and other relevant stakeholders involved in the training and continuing education of ECE and YSC. This cooperation promotes the exchange of best practices to sustainably improve the quality of training in these professions. The EduPASS partnership consortium consists of **seven project partners** working together to achieve the project’s objectives and produce specific results based on their respective expertise. The partners include three institutions from Luxembourg – **the University of Luxembourg, Institut national de l’activité physique et des sports (INAPS) and Conseil Européen des Recherches en Education Physique et Sportive (CEREPS)** – as well as two partners from Spain – **the University of Seville and Valgo Sport Consulting**. The consortium is complemented by the **Willibald Gebhardt Institute** from Germany and **Sport Ireland Coaching**.

The EduPASS partners completed a comprehensive assessment of the education and training of ECE and YSC in Europe. The project partners conducted a literature review and the EduPASS team conducted a Delphi study to reach a consensus among European experts in the field of PAMPS on competence-based training for ECE and YSC. The aim was to identify the most relevant competencies in the areas of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that are crucial for educational programmes designed to train ECE in non-formal settings and YSC in informal contexts. The project partners contacted national experts and invited them to share their knowledge of good practice in training. Based on the feedback from these experts, specific recommendations were developed. These findings were incorporated into the intellectual outputs **R#1, the literature review and the Delphi study, and R#2 Recommendations on Educator and Coach Education and Training**, and formed the basis for the professional profiles of ECE and YSC as well as the theoretical and methodological framework for structuring the educational processes for coaches and educators.

A main part of the project was the creation of a comprehensive competency-based profile for ECE and YSC. **These profiles clearly define the required competencies (R#3)** to ensure that professionals in education have the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and values to work effectively. In the following chapter, the respective profiles for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches are presented. In addition, a **theoretical and methodological framework (R#4)** was developed that structures the training and continuing education of ECE and YSC. This framework serves as a guide for the design of training programmes and ensures that they meet the current requirements of the education sector. These measures not only improve the quality of the training, but also ensure that educators and coaches are optimally prepared for their tasks.

Another important part of the project was the development of a **modular curriculum for educational programmes (R#5)** that can potentially be implemented in higher-education (at the bachelor's and/or master's level), as well as for the training and continuing education of ECE and YSC in non-higher education settings (for example, continuing education or National Governing Bodies of sport). This curriculum was designed to be flexible enough to meet the diverse needs of individual learners, educational institutions, and respective national contexts. To facilitate access to these valuable educational resources, a user-friendly **Online Teaching Platform** was set up to provide open access to the modules and course content.

Furthermore, an evaluation tool has been developed to assess modular programmes, courses, and teaching units. Evaluation promotes the continuous improvement of programmes and training offered and ensures that they meet current requirements as well as participants' needs. Details on the development of the **EduPASS Evaluation Tool** can be found under **R#6**. The evaluation tool was used at both EduPASS Learning, Teaching and Training (LTT)

events in Dublin and Luxembourg, which served to test the first developed EduPASS modules with actual (student) learners. The evaluation results of the learners and teachers that attended the two EduPASS LTT events are documented in the **Intellectual Output R#7**.

Through these measures, EduPASS contributes to improving quality education for professionals involved in PAMPS, thus positively influencing the development of children and young people in different social contexts. Strengthening the skills of ECE and YSC is crucial to creating an active and healthy society and physically literate individuals.

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Pathway of EduPASS

Figure 01.: Pathway of EduPASS project implementation

3. THE EduPASS COMPETENCY-BASED PROFILES

As part of the project, the EduPASS partners developed profiles for Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and Youth Sport Coaches (YSC) based on the core competence requirements for providing Physical Activity, Movement, Play, and Sport (PAMPS) in informal and non-formal environments. The choice of competencies was informed by the influential OECD “DeSeCo” (Definition and Selection of Competencies) model (Ananiadou & Claro, 2009).

Therefore, both profiles focus on the following aspects:

Knowledge: includes theoretical concepts and ideas, in addition to practical frameworks based on the experience of having performed in the relevant settings;

Skills: the abilities and capacities to carry out processes and be able to use one’s knowledge in a responsible way to achieve a goal;

Attitudes: learned tendencies or readiness to evaluate things or react to some ideas, people, or situations in specific ways, either consciously or unconsciously. Attitudes are underpinned by values and beliefs and influence behaviour;

Values: principles and core beliefs shared by individuals and groups that guide and motivate attitudes, choices, and behaviour and serve as broad guidelines for social life.

As a result of the **Delphi Study** conducted in R#1, eight competencies were identified for the respective KSAV in the profiles. Based on the five core competencies in each KSAV, the profile of a YSC or ECE can be summarized in the following tables. The numbers in brackets indicate the level of agreement among the experts who participated in the Delphi study: the higher the number, the greater the level of agreement (9 = highest value).

The other competencies (among the TOP 5) from the Delphi study are listed in **R#4 Theoretical and Methodological Framework** of ECE and YSC Education, which allows for adaptation to national/regional contexts and/or different phases of education and training for Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and Youth Sport Coaches (YSC).

Table 01.: Competency-based profile for Early Childhood Educators, EduPASS Intellectual Output R#3

Competency-based profile: Early Childhood Educator			
Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes	Values
<p>Motivation (8.65) Passionate and dedicated approach to fostering a dynamic learning environment</p>	<p>Communication skills (8.7) The ability to convey complex content in a way that is both child-friendly and engaging, and to create an interactive learning environment</p>	<p>Positive Attitude (8.61) A consistently optimistic and enthusiastic approach to teaching and learning</p>	<p>Fair Play (8.43) A commitment to integrity, honesty, and sportsmanship in education</p>
<p>Awareness of participants' needs (8.43) Ability to adapt and respond to the diverse requirements of students</p>	<p>Ability to create a positive learning environment (8.57) The ability to create a supportive and motivating learning environment in which children feel comfortable and can develop their joy of learning</p>	<p>Motivation (8.52) A strong drive and dedication to personal and professional growth</p>	<p>Ethical Practice (8.35) A focus on ethical behavior and decision-making</p>
<p>Pedagogical knowledge (8.22) Strong foundation in teaching methods and strategies to deliver content in accessible and impactful ways</p>	<p>Conflict resolution skills (8.43) The ability to constructively resolve conflicts between children and promote harmonious coexistence</p>	<p>Respect (8.48) A commitment to treating all individuals with dignity and consideration</p>	<p>Respect (8.22) Treating all individuals with dignity and kindness</p>
<p>Understanding of child development (8.17) Insights for adapting learning experiences to match students' developmental stages</p>	<p>Ability to motivate young people (8.39) The ability to inspire children and awaken their joy of learning</p>	<p>Empathy (8.35) A deep capacity for understanding and sharing the feelings of others</p>	<p>Inclusion (8.17) Embracing diversity and creating an inclusive learning environment</p>
<p>Recognition of individual differences (8.13) Commitment to inclusion and personalization of education to meet each child's unique needs and learning styles</p>	<p>Observation skills (8.22) The ability to recognize and respond to subtle behaviors in children in order to meet individual needs</p>	<p>Valuing Individual Differences (8.3) An appreciation for the diverse backgrounds and abilities of students</p>	<p>Responsibility (8.17) Understanding the impact of their role and setting a positive example</p>

Table 02.: Competency-based profile for Youth Sport Coaches, EduPASS Intellectual Output R#3

Competency-based profile: Youth Sport Coach			
Knowledge	Skills	Attitudes	Values
Understanding of interests and preferences (7.87) Ability to motivate young athletes through activities that match their individual interests and inclinations	Communication Skills (8.3) Effectively articulates instructions, provides feedback, and interacts with young athletes	Respect for Children's Needs (8.39) A commitment to understanding and valuing the unique preferences and requirements of each child	Ethical Behavior (8.3) A commitment to fair play, honesty, and integrity
Knowledge of basic motor development (7.83) Strategic approach to improving physical abilities that are important for participating in movement activities in early childhood	Promoting Fun and Enjoyment (8.3) Creates a positive and engaging sports environment	Enthusiasm (8.35) A passionate and energetic approach to coaching	Respect (8.26) Valuing all individuals involved in the sporting environment
Group dynamics and social interaction (7.74) Ability to promote cooperative play among young athletes, which improves children's social skills and creates a supportive, inclusive sports environment	Conflict Management Skills (8.09) Resolves disagreements and maintains a harmonious atmosphere	Creativity (8.3) The ability to design engaging and innovative training sessions	Fair Play (8.22) Upholding the spirit of the game and honest competition
Learning-centered approaches (7.52) Commitment to adapting coaching strategies to each child's diverse needs and learning pace to ensure an enriching and fun introduction to sport	Cooperation Skills (8.04) Encourages teamwork and collaboration among young athletes	Cooperation (8.26) A focus on teamwork and collaborative values	Cooperation (8.22) Encouraging teamwork and collaboration
Basic pedagogical knowledge (7.43) Fundamental understanding of educational principles that inform the YSC's strategies for instruction and engagement, ensuring that each young athlete's journey in sport is supportive, effective and development-oriented	Teaching/Pedagogical Skills (8.0) Employs effective teaching methods to cater to young learners	Motivation (8.26) The ability to inspire and encourage young athletes	Empathy (7.96) Understanding and sharing the feelings of others

In addition, a modular theoretical and methodological framework has been developed that serves as a basis for all professionals responsible for implementing PAMPS programmes. The competency-based profile served as a starting point for developing this theoretical and methodological framework for

training ECE and YSC. If implemented accordingly, it ensures that they have the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and values to be successful in delivering high-quality PAMPS.

Further details can be found in **R#3 ECE and YSC profile**.

3.1. SPAIN & IRELAND: CHALLENGES FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION¹

In addressing future challenges for Early Childhood Education in Europe two essential approaches in care taking and learning from Spain and Ireland (Pons et al., 2016; Viscarro et al., 2012; Woods et al., 2021; O`Siorain et al., 2024) may be worth exploring to inform assessment of contextual challenges in other countries in Europe. It is essential to incorporate emerging trends in pedagogy and technology that can add value to early development of children. There are different approaches for learning and development in early childhood. For the aspired **holistic development with inclusion** of all young children in EduPASS, a combination of different approaches is recommended. This should include **emotional education within an active learning approach** (e.g., O`Siorain et al., 2024) and **creative thinking with an experimental learning approach** (e.g., Woods et al., 2021) as two main pillars in day care and interactive learning with peers and workload of early childhood educators.

Emotional education and active learning have proven to be effective tools for enhancing children's social and conflict-resolution skills, creating an environment where they feel safe and understood. Building this specific objective into ECE education and training, of course will also affect, which Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes, and Values are prioritized in delivering the ECE programme.

Another important aspect to consider for ECE education and training is the introduction of methodologies that encourage **creative thinking and experiential learning**. Implementing flexible and adaptable learning spaces—such as sensory exploration workshops or symbolic play areas—fosters both types of **active as well as experimental learning** where children are engaged participants in their own discovery process.

This conceptual frame not only improves concept comprehension and retention, but also develops critical thinking and creativity. Again, this specific focus will likely be reflected in specific Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes, and Values being more prominent than others in the specific ECE profile and the respective education and training programme for early childhood educators.

For both types of learning in early childhood across all contexts, it seems evident that Early Childhood Educator training and education must continue to evolve towards an **inclusive approach**, where educational centres serve as spaces of equal opportunity. This means not only ensuring equitable access but also designing specific support programmes for families and children with diverse needs, promoting an adaptive learning environment that respects individuality and encourages the active participation of all. As such, the EduPASS ECE profile as well as the core modular ECE training and education programme accessible on the Online Teaching Platform place a heavy emphasis on diversity, inclusion and safeguarding.

¹The project partner information for this example was provided by Francis Ries (University of Seville, Spain). The text has been edited by Roland Naul (Willibald Gebhardt Institute, Germany).

An **inclusive approach for all children** should also provide nowadays two modern methods and teaching strategies: **digitalization and gamification**. In terms of **digitalization**, incorporating digital tools in a controlled and tailored way can also be beneficial. For example, interactive educational apps designed specifically for children ages 0 to 6 can stimulate autonomous learning and develop basic technological skills. However, it is essential that this integration respects guidelines for appropriate screen use in early childhood, with a focus on balance and supervision. Especially in the context of Physical Activity, Movement, Play, and Sport, digitalization could be potentially counterproductive – yet, “**gamification**” of certain activities could very well yield positive effects.

Providing future Early Childhood Educators with strong education and training while teaching them the necessity of extended competencies of Knowledge, Skills, Attitudes, and Values that they (as well as those that their learners, i.e., the children) need to develop in Physical Activity, Movement, Play, and Sport (PAMPS) is a milestone of the EduPASS core educational curriculum. Carrying out well directed and

planned PAMPS programs in ECE is essential for children’s physical, social, and emotional well-being, and for increasing adherence to physical exercise and developing physical literacy.

In this example of EduPASS-informed practice we have shared specific current needs, cultural aspects, and societal trends that currently affect children and youth as an example in Spain and Ireland, and as such also the competencies required from educators working with them. We hope our twofold conceptual examples from Spain and Ireland will help stakeholders from other countries to engage and apply similar reflective processes, that will help to implement a context-specific, tailored approach to ECE education and training in their EU countries.

3.2. LUXEMBOURG: NATIONAL PROGRAMME INITIATIVES ACROSS YSC AND ECE SETTINGS²

FUNDamentals Team Lëtzebuerg

When preparing and delivering the EduPASS LTT event in Luxembourg, some of the content that was piloted by the EduPASS project partners was also contributed by Luxembourg’s National Institute for Physical Activity and Sport (INAPS). Specifically, the “FUNDamentals Team Luxembourg” concept and content was shared, and subsequently used as a best-practice example for EduPASS module development for Early Childhood Educator training. The key aspects of “FUNDamentals Team Luxembourg” are shared here again, highlighting how Luxembourg’s approach to educating and training stakeholders involved in non-formal settings where Physical Activity, Movement, Play, and Sport (PAMPS) are offered aligns with the EduPASS ECE profile and modular education and training programme.

FUNDamentals Team Lëtzebuerg (FTL) is an integral part of the LTAD – Lëtzebuerg leeft Sport (2020) conceptual framework³ and aligns with the objectives pursued by the concept jointly developed by the Ministry of Sports and the Ministry of National Education, Children and Youth regarding motor, physical, and sports education for children aged 0 to 12 years (2018).

The ultimate goal is to support actors involved in children’s motor skills – especially parents, school staff, education and care structures, as well as technical staff of organized sports – in **promoting the joy of moving regularly and appropriately from an early age.**

FTL revolves around an illustrated adventure composed of more than 300 physical activities for children covering 12 groups of basic motor skills with the incorporation of reference characters embodying the FUNDamentals Team Lëtzebuerg.

Furthermore, FTL has given rise to a large number of related projects, creating a shared enthusiasm among all those involved in developing children’s motor skills. Numerous videos of the activities, for example, have been filmed and published free of charge and made available to everyone on the ‘LTAD’ mobile application.

As the highlighted parts of the project description illustrate, there is much overlap in the general approach – focusing on fundamentals – as well as the ultimate goal – promoting joy and fun as well as regular, life-long activity – between the FTL and EduPASS projects. Thus, competencies

²The project partner information for this example was provided by Tom Schmit (INAPS, Luxembourg).

³The LTAD conceptual framework is available for download in German and French in the Grand Duchy of Luxembourg’s SPORTS Portal, which is the property of the Luxembourg State and is published by the Ministry of Sport. LTAD in German: www.sports.public.lu/dam-assets/fr/publications/DE-LTAD-Rahmenkonzept.pdf; LTAD in French: www.sports.public.lu/dam-assets/fr/publications/FR-LTAD-Rahmenkonzept.pdf

that will be part of the learning objectives for those completing the FTL, align with the ECE and YSC profiles.

Motor Skills Coach Education Programme

Specifically for informal settings like sport clubs, Luxembourg's National Institute for Physical Activity and Sport (INAPS) has developed a Motor Skill Coach Education programme. Just as in the EduPASS project, the Motor Skill Coach training adopts a multidisciplinary approach that focuses on children's motor skills across contexts rather than implementing a sport specific approach

The INAPS education programme for motor skills coaches covers topics such as **child development** and the resulting requirements for the specialist or coach, as well as the **planning and implementation of physical and sports activities** for children.

These topics are **addressed theoretically** and then **applied in practice**, creating a constant **link between theory and practice**. The programme is designed to be as practical and playful as possible. Candidates should leave with a head full of game ideas that they can immediately implement with their group the next day.

Additionally, they will learn to adapt or modify these game ideas to suit their group or evolve with it. There are no prerequisites for this programme; it is open to anyone who leads or wishes to lead physical or sports activities with children.

The programme was initially designed for coaches supervising activities for children aged 0 to 12 and is currently being revised into two complementary training programmes: the first for coaches supervising children aged 0 to 6, the

second for coaches supervising children aged 6 to 12. Each course consists of at least 120 training units and is certified by a Brevet d'Etat (state certificate).

Motor Skills Coach for children aged 0 – 6

Learning Objectives: Participants know the **basics of motor, sensory, and emotional development** in early childhood. They are familiar with **methods for involving parents** in the promotion of movement in early childhood and understand the importance of this involvement.

They know the basics of **attachment-promoting play and movement** concepts, the development and importance of play behaviour in early childhood, concrete **play and movement topics** appropriate to the respective development topics in early childhood, and the basics of first aid for children. Participants can **develop, plan, and implement holistic movement offers** in early childhood. They are able to create methodological planning concepts and implement them within the respective framework, whether it be sport, non-formal education or formal education. They can **reflect** on their work consciously and adapt it to the needs of the participants. They are capable of involving parents participatively in the movement offers and providing parents with basic information on healthy child development. They can put various sports directions in the context of early childhood movement promotion and **counteract risks and deficiencies in the movement development** of toddlers through preventive offers. Participants **meet children and parents with appreciation and joy**. They act with **respect** for the possibilities of the participants. They primarily **convey the joy of movement**. They see themselves as initiators in the field of primary prevention and **practice continuous self-reflection** as well as intervention and supervision.

Motor Skills Coach for children aged 6 – 12

Learning Objectives: The education programme for motor skills coaches for ages 6 – 12 is a continuation of the early childhood programme, focusing on the next stage of development. It emphasizes the **planning and implementation of physical and sports activities** for children aged 6 to 12 years. The programme comprises 120 education units spread over 9 weekends. Participants will delve deeper into the **theoretical aspects of child development** and the **practical application of this knowledge** in sports and physical activities. They will learn to create a bridge between theory and practice, ensuring that their **sessions are both educational and enjoyable**. The programme aims to equip specialists with a variety of game ideas and activities that can be immediately implemented and adapted to suit the needs of their groups.

In the brief programme description, we have highlighted again various aspects that align with the EduPASS Youth Sport Coach (YSC) profile and training programme approach. The highlighted text in bold reflects learning objectives included in the EduPASS modular programme that was developed based on the competency-based profiles for YSC. The highlighted text in bold red points to specific competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) that align with the specific EduPASS YSC profile.

We feel that studying these two stakeholder examples of programmes developed in Luxembourg for non-formal and informal PAMPS settings, will provide readers with valuable information and context to answer the following reflection questions, provided in the next chapter.

3.3. REFLECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION QUESTIONS / EXERCISE

Consider the following reflection questions to evaluate the education and training programmes you deliver against the EduPASS Competency-based Profiles for Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators.

Is your current education and training programme based on a competency-based profile?

YES

NO

**If yes, what does the profile look like?
Where are similarities and differences?**

What contextual factors might be related to some of these differences?

Can you identify any competencies from EduPASS the Profiles that you would consider necessary to add to your profile?

If no, what other methodological framework is your programme based on?

*Now it's
your turn!*

What are some key strengths of that specific methodological approach?

What contextual factors might help you in doing so?

What added benefit could adopting the EduPASS competency-based profile yield for your current education and training programme?

What contextual factors might make this difficult?

4. THE EduPASS COMPETENCY-BASED MODULAR PROGRAMME

Based on the ECE and YSC profiles presented in Chapter 3 the EduPASS partners set to develop a comprehensive Online Teaching Platform. Content available on the Platform is aligned with the methodological and theoretical framework developed by the EduPASS partners. Implementing those modules as part of ECE and YSC Development Programmes is intended to foster professional development aligned with the core competencies identified within the EduPASS Delphi Study. When drafting the EduPASS ECE and YSC modular programmes, the partners considered alignment with the core competencies identified. Any professional training and development programme should be based on a well-adjusted combination of theoretical, practical and professional work across the period of the programme. It should embrace practical activities, educational and teaching sciences, natural and biological sciences, social sciences/humanities, scientific work, and field-based practice, all reflected in the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) methodological framework for course design.

Universal Design for Learning⁴ (UDL; La et al., 2018) is a framework that guides the design of courses and learning environments to appeal to the largest number of students/learners. When implementing a module, it helps to anticipate and to plan for all learners from the beginning, making sure that the greatest range of students can access and engage in learning. The EduPASS project partners implemented a variety of methodologies for various means of action and expression as well as representation suggested by UDL as part of the two Learning, Teaching, Training (LTT) events held with student learners in **Dublin** and **Luxembourg**. Based on the evaluation of the LTT events, adjustments to

the respective EduPASS Online Teaching Platform content on the module, course, or teaching unit level were implemented.

Linking the modular programme content to the competency profile, it is important to recall the four different sectors of competencies adopted for the EduPASS project: knowledge (K), skills (S), attitudes (A) and values (V). All six core modules for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches are related to these four sectors of competence, often with cross-competencies in each of the six core modules (e.g., knowledge & skills; attitudes & values; knowledge & attitudes & values; skills & attitudes & values). There is no ranking of importance of the four sectors of competencies and each core module may be selected for teaching and learning independently from each other according to the kind of group and pre-level of development of members of the group/class. However, a certain pathway of process to teach and to learn inside the set of the six core modules may support the total outcome of teaching and learning step by step, module to module for Youth Sport Coaches as well as for Early Childhood Educators.

The following section presents the six core modules for each profile and the associated areas of competence. Each module is comprised of at least two courses, and each course has at least two teaching units. In total, each module has 30 teaching hours and thus comprises one ECTS credit. A template of the module and course structure has been developed to provide a clear overview. In addition to a description of the module and course content, it includes the scope of the module, the type of teaching and materials/resources, and the learning outcomes for YSC / ECE and the learners.

⁴A comprehensive list of suggested methodologies can be found in Tables 2 & 3 in EduPASS **R#4 – Theoretical and Methodological Framework for ECE and YSC Education**.

However, to reiterate from the introduction, a key point to consider for stakeholders in ECE and YSC training and development is that the EduPASS Online Teaching Platform is primarily intended as a resource that provides competency-based training modules that were identified and developed within a comprehensive theoretical and methodological approach.

From our perspective, the YSC and ECE modular education and training programmes are not necessarily intended to be seen/used as a complete, stand-alone ECE/YSC development curriculum. As most stakeholders accessing the EduPASS Online Teaching Platform will most likely already have some form of training programme already in place, we think the added value for interested stakeholders lies more in a process of evaluating what they deliver against what we have created and see where ...

- ... can they improve content they already deliver based on our suggested materials?
- ... do they already have content well covered?
- ... do they have gaps and should consider adding certain modules/courses/teaching units?

Further details can be found in **R#4 Theoretical and Methodological Framework for ECE and YSC Education and Training.**

Table 03.: Connections of the EduPASS core modules with the categories of competencies for Early Childhood Educators

Early Childhood Educator · non-formal setting		
Core module	Main competency area	Second competency area
Daily Physical Activity and Play	K: Motivation S: Communication skills A: Positive attitude V: Respect & Inclusion	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Motivating young people A: Motivation V: Promoting positive changes
Principles of Educating Children	K: Participants' needs S: Communication skills A: Motivation V: Fair play	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Providing a positive learning environment A: Positive attitude V: Ethical practice
Inclusive Teaching	K: Participants' needs S: Providing a positive learning environment A: Empathy V: Inclusion	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Organizational skills A: Positive attitude V: Respect
Fundamental Movement Skills and Play & Motor Skills Assessment	K: Child development S: Communication skills A: Motivation V: Fair play	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Providing a positive learning environment A: Positive attitude V: Ethical practice
Hands-on Teaching	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Communication skills A: Empathy V: Respect	K: Participants' needs S: Organizational skills A: Positive attitude V: Cooperation (Community engagement)
Plan, Reflect and Learn	K: Participants' needs S: Providing a positive learning environment A: Positive attitude V: Respect	K: Pedagogical knowledge S: Communication skills A: Motivation V: Responsibility

Table 04.: Connections of the EduPASS core modules with the categories of competencies for Youth Sport Coaches

Youth Sport Coach · informal setting		
Core module	Main competency area	Second competency area
Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment	K: Child's interests and preferences S: Promoting fun and enjoyment A: Enthusiasm V: Cooperation	K: Knowledge of basic motor development S: Communication skills A: Creativity V: Empathy
Principles of Coaching Children	K: Child development S: Promoting fun and enjoyment A: Respecting children's needs and interests V: Ethical behaviour	K: Group Dynamics & Social Interaction S: Communication skills A: Motivating V: Respect
Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding	K: Child's interests and preferences S: Communication skills A: Respecting children's needs and interests V: Respect	K: Learner-centred approaches S: Cooperation skills A: Cooperation V: Empathy
Fundamental Movement Skills and Play	K: Knowledge of basic motor development S: Teaching / pedagogical skills A: Motivating V: Fair play	K: Basic pedagogical knowledge S: Cooperation skills A: Creativity V: Cooperation
Hands-on Coaching	K: Basic pedagogical knowledge S: Promoting fun and enjoyment A: Enthusiasm V: Fair play	K: Learner-centred approaches S: Teaching / pedagogical skills A: Respecting children's needs and interests V: Empathy
Plan, Reflect and Learn	K: Knowledge of activities in informal PAMPS S: Coaching / pedagogical skills A: Creativity V: Ethical behaviour	K: The role of play & exploration S: Communication skills A: Motivating V: Fair play

4.1. CURRICULAR FLEXIBILITY OF EduPASS CORE MODULES⁵

The EduPASS modular education and training programmes for Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and Youth Sport Coaches (YSC) consist each of six core modules for the European dimension. The core modules have been designed and structured into a set of different courses per module and the number of courses vary inside both job profiles. All courses are built from different kinds of teaching units, which include lectures, seminars, workshops and self-directed homework studies. Within the EduPASS programmes, total amount of teaching units and working hours for each YSC and ECE module was limited to 30 hrs workload for all 12 core modules. However, the internal workload of the different kinds of teaching units (e.g., hrs of lectures, hrs for self-directed studies) also vary between courses in both job profiles. The number of courses within a module and the number of different kinds of teaching units (hours) in a course is recommended by the project consortium of the EduPASS project.

However, it is important to highlight that the EduPASS programmes as well as the individual modules and courses for YSC and ECE can be applied with **internal and external curricular flexibility**, based on the contextual factors a stakeholder needs to consider.

Internal curricular flexibility is linked to priorities of an institution implementing YSC or ECE programmes, which wants to distribute the EduPASS structure of workloads (hrs) within a specific course and its respective teaching units differently than recommended within the **EduPASS Online Teaching Platform**.

Specifically, this would mean that within a course's teaching units more or less lectures, more or less workshops and/or more or less self-directed studies are included. To make sure that the overall workload of 30 hrs for the module remains the same, certain learning/teaching modalities may be extended in hrs. if another kind within the teaching unit will be reduced in hrs.

Reasons to adapt the number of hours for specific learning/teaching modalities might be reflected in

- learner preferences and learning styles
- learners' prior experience and educational level
- cultural factors within the organization, country
- time frame of the education and training programme (i.e., compact course or longer duration with teaching units over multiple months)
- for a National Sport Federation setting, specifically: spreading the learning over a number of coach education levels

⁵This example has been developed by Roland Naul (Willibald Gebhardt Institute, Germany) and edited by Sebastian Brueckner (Willibald Gebhardt Institute, Germany).

External curricular flexibility is linked to the educational/training level of the institution which offers the YSC/ECE education and training programme. In many EU-countries training institutions for Early Childhood Educators are different kinds of secondary vocational schools/ Further Education colleges. For coach education training, however, only a limited number of higher-education-based Coaching Education programmes exist. In many countries, Youth Sport Coach education and training is offered at lower licence levels by regional, state, or national non-governmental sport associations.

While our recommended EduPASS core modules are all limited to 30 hrs workload, obviously less time constraints exist within a comprehensive vocational school or higher-education setting compared to ones offered by sport associations.

In this context, it is worth noting, that recently higher learning institutes across EU-countries also started to offer degree programmes for Early Childhood Educators separately or integrated into

bachelor studies of education (e.g., at Universities of Applied Sciences or Teacher Colleges). But there are also private higher-learning institutes and governmental based organizations, which offer study courses to achieve higher licences for Youth Sport Coaches.

For these education and training institutes external curricular flexibility means to adapt and extend the EduPASS YSC/ECE core modules up to a workload of 60 hrs, which aligns with 2 ECTS in the higher-education ECTS system (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System).

Specific examples for contexts, where EduPASS modules might be extended from 30 working hrs (1 ECTS) to 60 working hours (2 ECTS) have already been mentioned. However, it should also be noted that, specifically for educational and training pathways implemented by sport associations for Youth Sport Coach training, internal and external flexibility is certainly equally relevant and important.

4.2. IRELAND: EduPASS YOUTH SPORT COACHING MODULE REVIEW FROM A HIGHER EDUCATION PERSPECTIVE

Following the EduPASS National Multiplier Event in Ireland on October 07, 2024, one attendee⁶ reviewed the EduPASS Youth Sport Coaching Modules from the perspective of using the modules and resources in their work in higher education.

The project partners include this example in the EduPASS Handbook as it reflects the approach in which those engaging with the project’s Online Teaching Platform content would ‘tailor’ or adapt

the resources and materials available there to their own context, in a specific country, national federation, or in this case, in higher education.

The following are the observations accompanied by comments from the project partners.

Heading and Observations	Project Partner Comments
<p>Programme title: My perception when I see a title like “Youth Sport Coaching” is Teenagers or 12+. As an outsider looking in, I’m not sure Youth Sport Coach is the most suitable title.</p>	<p>As part of the project, while some conceptual work was done with a focus on U12s, the work also has relevance for the teenage years, adolescents and young athletes.</p>
<p>Consistency of terms: In the introduction to the course in the title it says “Youth”, but underneath it refers to “youth”, “children”, “young athletes”. In other areas of modules there are references to “adolescents”, “young people”. It might be an idea to have an explanation of each term at the end or beginning of the module/ introduction but that for consistency the modules themselves use just one term?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project work has relevance for the teenage years, adolescents and young athletes. • Some terms can be seen as inter-changeable. • A user engaging in the project should be consistent with the term(s) used in their context/country.

⁶The reviewer was Joe Meegan, Lecturer, Sport Management & Coaching, Department of Hospitality, Tourism & Leisure, Technical University of the Shannon (TUS), Athlone. The project partner comments were made by Sebastian Brueckner (Willibald Gebhardt Institute) and Declan O’Leary (Sport Ireland Coaching).

Heading and Observations

Project Partner Comments

Programme learning outcomes:

Page 7-8 of the modules read well. Has the design team mapped these Programme Learning Outcomes to specific Module Learning Outcomes or units within modules? Though often a tedious job it does help give confidence to the reader and the developers that there is a clear connection between the overall focus of the course and the specifics that make it up.

The partners have sought to thread the learning outcomes from programme to module to teaching unit.

We encourage stakeholders who engage with the resources, that they apply such a mapping process, so that they can adapt the EduPASS materials for use in their respective context.

Time commitment:

Reading each module and looking at the referenced content, there are elements that have a lot of content with quite limited hours.

I realise that giving an hour total to content that has not yet been delivered is challenging but might be an area that will need addressing when reviewing the first cohort of delivery.

This comment is accurate. The project aim was not to implement the modules. The project aimed to clarify the role of the YSC. Then to develop modules that would prepare learners for that role.

Stakeholders should adapt the EduPASS materials for use in their respective context, and that would certainly entail explicitly mapping out the specific working hours per content for each section.

Delivery at 3rd level⁷:

There is so much useful content in the modules, a lot of which we deliver but not structured in the way this programme is. As noted above there is a lot of material for what is already a lot of hours per module. It could be difficult to build into existing courses, and with the high delivery hours it would be feasible to deliver it alongside a 3rd level course. Also, some time would need to be spent on identifying how to build in some methods of assessment to suit the 3rd level structure?

This is exactly the topic of transferability into practice, and what we are aiming at with the handbook in the project.

Each stakeholder would need to consider these issues and adapt the project resources for their context.

This would truly be “EduPASS in Practice”, as discussed in the Example of EduPASS-informed Practice III: Curricular Flexibility.

⁷Third-level education in the Republic of Ireland includes all education after second-level, encompassing higher education in universities and colleges and further education on Post Leaving Certificate (PLC) and other courses.

Heading and Observations	Project Partner Comments
<p>Safeguarding: Module 3 on “Safeguarding” is a very important area for coaches to cover. Depending on the specific-country context, there could be an argument for this section to be removed as they will cover safeguarding on their safeguarding course.</p>	<p><i>This type of engagement in the specific adapting of modules is how the project partners see the EduPASS resources being used.</i></p> <p><i>There are many programmes throughout Europe, where safeguarding isn’t highlighted so it was included in the project.</i></p>
<p>Elite youth sports pathway: Is there an argument for some reference to the path from participation to “high level/elite sport” in the mid to late teenage years, areas like understanding burnout, the difficulties with affective talent identification for coaches, etc?</p>	<p><i>The EduPASS project is firmly fixed on what is described as Physical Activity, Movement, Play and Sport (PAMPS) context, so not on elite pathways.</i></p> <p><i>However, the child-centred approach, interpersonal coaching skills and relationship building advocated for in the project transfer to those pathways also.</i></p> <p><i>This is an adaptation that a stakeholder using the EduPASS resources may look to make.</i></p>

In conclusion, the process highlighted in the listings above illustrates – from our EduPASS project team’s perspective – perfectly, how we see stakeholders working and engaging with the materials developed: The EduPASS project approach and resources are designed to provide a framework and guidance for stakeholders who

are involved in the education and training of sport coaches and early childhood educators. The resources provided as a result of the EduPASS project should be subject to a mapping process that stakeholders actively engage in, to make sure they are tailored and adapted for use in the respective contexts, countries and/or sports.

4.3. GERMANY: ASSESSING FUTURE POTENTIAL FOR EduPASS-INFORMED PRACTICE IN GERMAN ECE CERTIFICATION PROGRAMMES⁸

During the EduPASS National Multiplier Event in Germany on September 12, 2024, multiple attendees expressed interest in exploring specific ways in which EduPASS results and resources might be implemented or integrated to improve Early Childhood Educator education and training programmes in their specific contexts. To share an example on how one specific stakeholder

from Germany, who's organization offers a certification programme for Early Childhood Educators in after-school programme-settings (in Germany: "All-day school setting"), we interviewed the stakeholder. The following are the main reflections and insights gained from the interview on the potential for EduPASS-informed ECE education and training practice.

Target Group

The specific **German certification programme** developed by the German partner consortium targets mostly the administrators, network partners and organizations that are responsible for creating opportunities, funding, structures, and concepts for successful after-school programmes. As such, Early Childhood Educators, that work directly with the children and offer Physical Activity, Movement, Play, and Sport (PAMPS) were not part of the certification programme – or only if they also held a broader administrative role within their organization.

However, the target group that the **EduPASS profile and modular programme** was developed for are Early Childhood Educators that work directly with the children and offer PAMPS activities.

Content

With the focus on the PAMPS work that Early Childhood Educators (ECE) engage in directly with the children they teach, the **EduPASS modular programme** for ECE education and training encompasses 180 working hours with an emphasis on (mostly pedagogical, interpersonal, leadership) knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed for direct classroom engagement as well as activity setup, delivery, reflection, and learning.

The **German certification programme** – due to the different target group – offers some modules that align with content developed as part of EduPASS (e.g., content from modules Fundamental Movement Skills and Play; Daily Physical Activity and Play; Inclusive Teaching; Principles of Teaching Children). However, an emphasis is also put on: 1) legal and safety issues in after-school settings, 2) quality management, 3) organizational, administrative and financial aspects of programme development. Overall, the certification programme also has a workload of 180 hours. However, less hours are focused on competencies needed to implement PAMPS as an ECE.

⁸This example has been developed by Dr. Sebastian Brueckner (Willibald Gebhardt Institute, Germany) based on an interview with Axel Binnenbruck, University of Muenster, Institute of Sport and Exercise Science, Project [sport-lernen.de](https://www.sport-lernen.de).

Content Development

The EduPASS project partners used a comprehensive, research and data driven, as well as consensus building approach when developing the respective competency-based profiles for Early Childhood Educators and Youth Sport Coaches. This is reflected in the literature review, integration of best-practice examples, data collection through an expert questionnaire, as well as the Delphi study consensus building that all underpinned the profiles, frameworks, and **EduPASS modular programmes** developed for ECE and YSC, respectively. Thus, the project team took a broad, European lens approach to develop results and resources and also aimed at alignment with the EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care (2014) as well as the European Sport Coaching Framework (2017).

The **German Certification programme** was developed using a bottom-up approach by the specific project partners to address a gap and need in Early Childhood Education after-school programme settings. Experts in after-school programme research and delivery contributed their expertise and knowledge to create the curriculum and content for programme delivery. Their main focus along with implementing findings and expertise build through their research in after-school programme settings was creating content tailored at addressing context specific needs for stakeholders in one of German's federal states.

Content Delivery

The **German Certification programme** intentionally chose a mix of in-person and online modules delivery. Being mindful of attendees' limited funding and time constraints this addresses specific contextual needs. Online modules reduce time and cost for travel as well as time of absence in attendees' organization's setting. Especially the more theoretical modules that cover legal, organizational, administrative and financial aspects lend themselves for online delivery.

The hands-on approach for ECE and YSC education and training adopted in the **EduPASS modular programmes** builds more on in-person interaction in a classroom or gym. The online/not in-person interactive segments that are built into the EduPASS programmes are limited to the self-directed learning. The in-person implementation is also how the modules were delivered when they were piloted during the two EduPASS LTT events in Luxembourg and Dublin. However the EduPASS partners acknowledge that any stakeholder exploring to adopt certain modules within their context, will also assess if some content can be delivered online instead of in-person, adopting a blended learning format.

Evaluation

Due to time constraints at the start of the first cohort no formal evaluation was implemented within the **German Certification programme** by the stakeholders. While Early Childhood Educator developers delivering the modules did engage in informal evaluation of their courses and teaching units, the partner consortium implementing the programme does aim to implement a formal review as well. The Evaluation Tool developed as part of the EduPASS project will likely be what informs this formal evaluation.

For the **EduPASS partners programme** evaluation was an essential part of programme creation (see **Chapter 5, page 34**). Not only module, course, and teaching unit content was piloted during the LTT events, but also the formal evaluation tools. As the example from the German stakeholder highlights, making a structured, formal evaluation tool available for ECE and YSC education and training programme review addresses a specific need for stakeholders interested in long-term quality management and improvement.

Potential for EduPASS-informed Future Adaptations and Activities

As highlighted above, each stakeholder must consider specific contextual factors when assessing the potential for adopting certain EduPASS results and resources in their respective education and training programme. As illustrated in our example, these factors include, but are not limited to:

- specific target group
- target group specific content and content delivery
- content development
- course development and scheduling

Specifically, the EduPASS evaluation tool seems to hold much potential for informing programme review, as often times stakeholders lack expertise, resources, and time to develop a comprehensive tool for programme evaluation. Yet, a combination of informal as well as formal evaluation is crucial to adapt.

Additionally, Willibald Gebhardt Institute as the German EduPASS project partner has been invited to join the group of stakeholders overseeing quality management of the German Certification programme. This will provide additional opportunities to advocate for key EduPASS results and resources being integrated when continuously developing and improving the after-school programme administrators' training programme as well when conceptualizing similar programmes for kindergarten stakeholder and settings.

4.4. REFLECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION QUESTIONS / EXERCISE

Consider the following reflection questions to evaluate the education and training programmes you deliver against the EduPASS Youth Sport Coaches and Early Childhood Educators modular education and training programme.

Which contextual factors characterize your unique ECE or YSC setting?

Who are your “learners”? Educators/coaches and/or administrators?

What prior education and training do your ECEs or YSCs have?

Which aspects, content & results of the EduPASS YSC and ECE modular education and training programmes are already included in the existing programmes in your country/context?

Now it's
your turn!

Which EduPASS YSC/ECE programme aspects, content & results are new and would you consider adopting?

What specific ways and possibilities are there to incorporate and implement EduPASS YSC/ECE aspects, content & results?

Which EduPASS YSC/ECE programmes aspects, content & results are missing, but are not essential in your country/context

What problems, issues might there be when trying to incorporate and implement EduPASS YSC/ECE aspects, content & results?

5. THE EduPASS EVALUATION TOOL⁹

As part of the EduPASS project, besides creating the content of the Online Teaching Platform (the core modules for Early Childhood Educator and Youth Sport Coach development programmes), the project partners also developed an Evaluation Tool. To ensure the quality of the modules and courses/teaching units that were implemented in the EduPASS pilot phase, the LTT events in **Dublin** and **Luxembourg** were evaluated with a specifically developed EduPASS Evaluation tool. The LTT evaluation allowed project partners to improve module/course/teaching unit content, thus directly contributing to high-quality Online Teaching Platform content.

However, part of the EduPASS objectives was also to develop an Evaluation Tool for educational formats in ECE and YSC programmes of learning. The idea is, as with the content of the Online Teaching Platform, for stakeholders offering professional development programmes for ECE and YSC, to compare their current evaluation tools and procedures with the ones developed by the EduPASS project partners.

The EduPASS evaluation method aimed to systematically assess education formats from a learner (Early Childhood Educators/ Youth Sport Coaches) perspective, as well as from an instructor (Early Childhood Educator-Developers/ Youth Sport Coach Educators) perspective. Two separate evaluation tools were developed for each learner and instructor perspective: one to evaluate complete training programmes/courses and one to assess single teaching units.

These tools were developed, based on the multi-level approach of Kirkpatrick's model, which evaluates training at four levels:

- 1) assessing participant satisfaction
- 2) self-assessed learning progress
- 3) behavioural changes
- 4) knowledge retention

Specific modifications were made to cater to the EduPASS programme as well as non-formal and informal PAMPS settings. Specifically, levels one to three of the model, namely "satisfaction and acceptance", "self-assessed learning progress", and "assessment of behavioural change through the teacher training" were emphasised.

The key aspects of the tool include:

Evaluation Tools Design: Two evaluation tools were developed with input from the EduPASS team members and included questionnaires targeting both coach educators and sport educators. The questionnaire covered three primary areas: demographics, event evaluation, and teaching unit assessment. A five-point Likert scale is used, and open-ended questions to capture qualitative feedback are included.

Structure: The questionnaires feature closed and open-ended questions about event organization, content delivery, implementation, participant experience and specific teaching unit features. Emphasis is placed on clarity, appropriateness of content, balance between theory and practice, and perceived impact on professional development. A Likert scale is used to assess participant responses, supplemented by open-ended questions for qualitative feedback.

⁹The project partner information for this example was provided by Manolis Adamakis (University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg).

Validation: The development included multiple expert feedback rounds with project partners, ensuring face and content validity. Items were reviewed for clarity, feasibility, and alignment with learning outcomes, resulting in a tool well-tailored for the EduPASS teaching units and events.

When we implemented the evaluation tools at the two LTT events in **Dublin** and **Luxembourg** using a validated survey proved very useful. The results allowed us to improve delivery of the Luxembourg LTT after reviewing feedback from LTT Dublin. Following the Luxembourg LTT, we subsequently further improved our Online Teaching Platform content.

Specifically, the results¹⁰ from our LTT evaluations underscored the importance of interactive and hands-on learning, a balanced approach between theory and practice, and the benefits of collaborative learning. Future, our participants (learners and instructors) suggested, development programmes could be further improved by:

- Increasing practical sessions, providing more reflective opportunities, as well as more clear guidelines on applying educational principles in different real-life scenarios.

- Offering more targeted feedback and critical analysis after sessions.
- Expanding teaching materials, including detailed notes and resources ahead of events.

The evaluation findings validate the success of EduPASS teaching units and development programmes, particularly in creating adaptable, effective educational tools for physical activity and sports education, with further refinements suggested to optimize future programmes and enhance the learning experience for participants. As a theoretically founded, structured, and validated tool, the EduPASS evaluation tools offers a valuable model for similar initiatives, highlighting the critical role of comprehensive assessment tools in refining educational programs in sports settings.

Stakeholders who offer professional development opportunities for ECE and YSC in non-formal and informal PAMPS settings are encouraged to consider how the **EduPASS Evaluation Tool** – accessible as adaptable Word file on the project website – might be implemented in their respective context. To reiterate from the Introduction:

We think the added value for interested stakeholders lies in a process of evaluating what they use currently for their programme evaluation against what we have created.

¹⁰You can read the evaluation results of the two LTTs in detail [here](#) (IO#7).

5.1. IRELAND: THE POTENTIAL USE OF THE EduPASS EVALUATION TOOL WITH NATIONAL GOVERNING BODIES (FEDERATIONS)¹¹

The EduPASS Evaluation Tool was very beneficial to the evaluation of the Learning, Teaching and Training events hosted for Youth Sports Coaches (Dublin) and Early Childhood Educators (Luxembourg) during the EduPASS project. The aim of this example is to consider how the evaluation tool developed by the EduPASS project partners could be used by National Governing Bodies (Federations) in Ireland that educate and train sports coaches. The evaluation of coach education is an essential component to ensuring that the education is beneficial to learners and it is also a means of applying the principles of continuous improvement to the education and training.

For context, in Ireland, much coach education is provided by National Governing Bodies (Federations). There are processes for programme validation, coach developer training and quality assurance which apply before a coach education award is approved to run and for coach certification. They are part of the **Coaching Development Programme for Ireland (CDPI)**, a series of coach education awards that increase in terms of commitment, time and coaching competencies (see table 05 below), with potential for each award to be integrated into a specific sport.

¹¹This review has been developed by: Vicki Guy, Coach Education Development Officer, Sport Ireland Coaching & Declan O’Leary, Coaching Development Manager, Sport Ireland Coaching.

Table 05.: Detailed Coaching Development Programme for Ireland (CDPI) structure and content

CDPI LEVEL	AIM	KEY CONTENT	DURATION
<p>Introduction to Coaching</p> <p><i>Role:</i> Assist in organising sessions</p>	<p>Arouse interest in coaching</p> <p>Introduction to basic coaching skills</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of coaching • Planning, organising and reviewing sessions • Ethics 	1 – 2 days
<p>Level 1</p> <p><i>Role:</i> Plan, implement and review sessions for children up to age 12; or children 13 –18 or adults</p>	Provide basic coaching skills relevant to fundamental/ early train to train stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning, organising, coaching and reviewing sessions • Technical, tactical, mental, physical, personal, lifestyle capacities (fundamental/early train to train stage) • Ethics 	20 – 40 hours, plus 5 – 15 hours logged experience followed by a minimum of 1 year coaching experience
<p>Level 2</p> <p><i>Role:</i> Plan, implement, review sessions for children up to age 18 or adults</p>	Provide coaching skills relevant to train to train/ early train to compete stage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning, organising, coaching and reviewing sessions/up to a season • Technical, tactical, mental, physical, personal, lifestyle capacities (train to train/early train to compete stage) • Ethics 	40 – 60 hours, plus 10 – 30 hours logged experience followed by a minimum of 2 years coaching experience
<p>Level 3 (Development)</p> <p><i>Role:</i> Lead programmes in clubs/NGBs for young people in sport</p>	Provide knowledge and skills to underpin coaching programmes for young people in clubs, NGBs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-depth treatment of Long-Term Athlete Development and of technical, tactical, physical, mental, personal, lifestyle issues for children in the 6 – 18 age range • Facilitation/tutoring skills • Systems design and management • Ethics 	200 – 240 hours over minimum of 1 year (minimum contact 75 hours) followed by a minimum of 2 years coaching experience
<p>Level 4 (Development)</p> <p><i>Role:</i> Oversee development programmes at national level</p>	Provide coaches with skills to design, implement and monitor national development programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long Term Athlete Development • Talent development • Systems design and management skills • Ethics 	1 year course full-time or 2 year part-time

OVERALL COMMENTS

In relation to the EduPASS Evaluation Tool, overall, Sport Ireland concluded that all three (3) parts of the evaluation tool can be beneficial.

Part 1: General Information

Part 2: Learning, Teaching Training Event

Part 3: Teaching Unit Content

It should be stated that the use of the evaluation tool would see it (similar to other EduPASS project outputs) be subject to adaptation to the context in which it is used. Also, it is envisaged that not all 3 parts may be used for all coach education events.

Examples of this could be:

For CDPI Levels – Intro, 1 and 2: On a full coach education course, Parts 1 and 2 could be completed once.

For CDPI Levels 3 and 4: As well as Parts 1 and Part 2, Part 3 could be done for separate teaching units.

CPD Opportunities: The CDPI also includes shorter CPD opportunities as workshops or webinars. For these, adapted Part 2, including the qualitative questions could be used.

GENERAL SPECIFIC COMMENTS

Title: Remove youth and just leave it as an evaluation tool for sport coaches. Use the title of the specific event that is being held.

Online Platform: The questions could be included on a platform for analysis purposes. Information on where the data would be stored and what software was used in the analysis would need to be available to coaches to comply with GDPR requirements in the EU.

SPECIFIC COMMENTS ABOUT PART 1 to 3:

Part 1: Add to title: General Information – About You and Your Coaching

Some of this information would be included in the application process to do a coach education course, which could benefit the coach developers delivering the course.

The data collected would be an interesting way to collect info on coaches in a sport, on an on-going basis. The headings could be amended to reflect country and sports specific questions.

Part 2: Learning, Teaching and Training Event

There may be a need to add another section on organisation related to the logistics for the event - communication, travel, parking, facility, equipment, A-V/sound, catering, other.

The questions would need to be adapted for use in their specific context, including the qualitative ones.

Part 3: Teaching Unit Content

Evaluating each of the teaching units can be valuable. Especially if a range of coach developers are used to deliver different teaching units on a course.

This information would be useful in an overall review of an award.

We hope this example of assessing applicability and added value of the EduPASS Evaluation Tools for a specific (national) Youth Sport Coach education and training context has been helpful in providing you as a reader with some ideas and procedures on how to assess potential benefits of those materials for your specific context. To help you engage with that process, we hope you will be able to make use of the Reflection Questions we provide in the following chapter.

Now it's
your turn!

5.2. REFLECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION QUESTIONS / EXERCISE

Consider the following reflection questions to review how you evaluate the education and training programmes you deliver against the EduPASS Evaluation Tool we have developed.

In general: Where can you improve the evaluation you have already implemented based on the suggested EduPASS Evaluation tools?

Which aspects and content of the EduPASS Evaluation Tools are already included in programme evaluation in your country/ context?

Where do you have gaps and should consider adding certain new aspects or content of the EduPASS Evaluation Tools?

What specific ways and possibilities are there to incorporate and implement EduPASS Evaluation Tool aspects, content?

What problems or issues might there be when trying to incorporate and implement EduPASS Evaluation Tool aspects or content?

6. SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR ECE AND YSC PROGRAMMES

We are starting to wind down our “Handbook and Guidance Material for the Implementation of the modular Early Childhood Educator (ECE) and Youth Sport Coach (YSC) Education and Training programme”. We hope that the information we have presented on the previous pages, the examples of EduPASS-informed practice, and the reflection questions have helped you to engage with the EduPASS results and materials – and review where your organization and the ECE/YSC education and training programme you are currently delivering, might benefit from adding on adopting EduPASS-informed practice.

To further assist with this process, and help you assess how well aligned your current programme is compared to the EduPASS modular programme for ECE/YSC education and training, we have developed an easy-to-use Self-Check Tool for

ECE and YSC Programme Review. The comprehensive tables and review steps can be found in **Appendix 1**.

For each of the six ECE/YSC EduPASS modules we have created a table that serves as a checklist. In a step-by-step process you can gauge alignment of your current programme with the modular EduPASS course structure and content. Modular content review is complemented by an assessment of the overall rating of alignment. Finally, we offer a rating scale where you can compare the balance between theory and practice within your programme delivery.

We hope that this additional Self-Check Tool for ECE and YSC Programme Review will make it even easier for you to engage with the materials provided in the EduPASS Online Teaching Platform.

7. CONCLUSION

The respective six EduPASS core modules for Early Childhood Educators (ECE) and for Youth Sport Coaches (YSC) education and training aim to equip and prepare educators and coaches to deliver high quality physical activity, movement, play and sport (PAMPS) for children and young people in non-formal (kindergarten, after-school programs) and in informal (sport clubs) settings. This EduPASS Handbook and Guidance Material developed as Intellectual Output #8 is designed to support the easy and flexible implementation of the modular education and training programme for Youth Sport Coaches in informal as well as Early Childhood Educators in non-formal learning setting.

Thus, stakeholders who are interested in implementing the content available in the **EduPASS Online Teaching Platform** in various settings, e.g., in different countries, educational settings or at different educational levels, should be supported in doing so, by engaging with this handbook.

We have chosen a multi-layered approach to facilitate this evaluation process of EduPASS materials against stakeholders' current education and training programmes:

- Illustrate through Examples of EduPASS-informed practice, how specific issues or questions that might arise when comparing one's current programme against the EduPASS modular programme could be addressed

- Provide specific Reflection Questions and Exercises to engage readers in this process
- Present a comprehensive Self-Check Tool that includes a detailed check list to assist in comparing one's current programme content against the EduPASS modules' content

This multi-layered approach – we hope – will help readers facilitate engaging with our EduPASS Online Teaching Platform materials – in a flexible way, where each reader might find an approach that provides especially useful for them.

The EduPASS project partners hope you enjoy exploring our programme resources and hope you succeed in adapting and implementing it in your own context. If you have any questions or comments, the partners will be happy to share their expertise and welcome your suggestions and feedback.

8. REFERENCES

- Ananiadou, K., & Magdolean, C. (2009). 21st century skills and competences for new millennium learners in OECD countries. *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 41. doi.org/10.1787/218525261154
- Lara-Bercial, S., North, J., Petrovic, P., Oltmanns, K., Minkhorst, J., Hämäläinen, K., & Livingstone, K. (2017). *The European sport coaching framework*. Human kinetics.
- European Commission (2014). Proposal for key principles of a Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care. *Report of the Working Group on Early Childhood Education and Care under the auspices of the European Commission*. Available at: www.opgroeien.be/sites/default/files/documenten/ecec-quality-framework_en.pdf
- La, H., Dyjur, P., & Bair, H. (2018). *Universal design for learning in higher education*. Taylor Institute for Teaching and Learning, University of Calgary.
- O'Siorain, L., Kernan, M. & McArdle, F. (2024). Disrupting the Aistear hour: Working towards play-based curriculum in early childhood classrooms in Irish primary schools. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 32(2), 288-302.
- Pons, R., & Arufe, V. (2016). Análisis descriptivo de las sesiones e instalaciones de psicomotricidad en el aula de educación infantil. *Sportis Scientific Technical Journal*, 2(1), 125-146. doi.org/10.17979/sportis.2016.2.1.1445
- Viscarro-Tomás, I., Antón-Rosera, M., & Cañabete-Ortiz, D. (2012). Perfil y formación de los profesionales que realizan la práctica psicomotriz en la etapa de educación infantil: El caso de las comarcas de Tarragona. *Educar*, 48(2), 321-344. doi.org/10.5565/rev/educar.28
- Woods, A., Mannion, A., & Garrity, S. (2021). Implementing Aistear – the Early Childhood Curriculum Framework Across Varied Settings: Experiences of Early Years Educators and Infant Primary School Teachers in the Irish Context. *Child Care in Practice*, 28(4), 671-690. doi.org/10.1080/13575279.2021.1920367

IMAGE REFERENCES

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SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACH AND EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR PROGRAMME

With the EduPASS Self-Check Tool, you can check which module content is already integrated into your training and development programme for Early Childhood Educators or Youth Sport Coaches.

For each module, there is a table that provides a detailed view of the courses. This allows you to compare directly, which content and practical phases already exist in your ECE and YSC training and development programme, and which content currently is not covered. There is also a table that helps you assess the amount of theoretical and practical content. Compared to the EduPASS modules, how much time is spent engaging with theoretical aspects, how much committed to practical experiences in your training and development programme?

Step 1: Select the educational programme you would like to check and compare.

Early Childhood Educators

start at page II

Youth Sport Coaches

start at page XVI

Step 2: Go through the following EduPASS **ECE/ YSC module checklists** and consider whether the theoretical content and practical phases listed are part of the training and continuing education programme you currently offer at your institution. Mark either the **YES** or **NO** column for

each item. The theoretical content or practical phases marked with “**No**” represent **gaps** in the training programme you currently offer.

Step 3: Transfer the results of your checklist for the individual modules to the ECE/YSC programme summary and get a complete assessment of how much EduPASS content is already included in your training and continuing education programme. Keeping in mind, however, that considering your unique context not every gap you identify must be addressed... it is your choice to make an informed decision now to do or do not address this gap.

Programme Summary Early Childhood Educators

page XV

Programme Summary Youth Sport Coaches

page XXXIII

Step 4: With the help of the **EduPASS Online Teaching Platform**, you can access specific content, that should help you addressing the gaps and potentially missing content in your programme. Download the modules for YSC or ECE as a PDF document and, if desired, the additional teaching materials (presentations and practical tools). Customize the module, course and teaching unit content for your respective setting and job profiles – have fun with it!

MODULE 1 · DAILY PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AND PLAY

Course 1.1 · Child Holistic Development		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Concept of holistic development		
	Specifics of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development at 3 – 6 years old children		
	The importance of holistic approach from the aspect of physical activity		
Practical content	Work in small groups for preparing teaching activities based on theoretical lectures and independent observations and work		
	Self-Directed Learning – Observing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Observing a particular child or several children independently at the age of 3 – 6 years · Focus observation of changes that occur in every developmental domain, identifying similarities and differences between different children 		

Course 1.2 · Importance of Physical Activity and Play for Children's Holistic Development and overall Well-being		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Focusing on the importance of daily physical activity in children for holistic development and overall health and well-being.		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Readings of evidence-based studies for the impact of physical activity or inactivity on children's health, well-being and overall development of children · Emphasis on study results and experiences and evidence during COVID-19 pandemics 		
Practical content	Work in small groups/focus groups discussion for preparing a toolkit with infographic slides for benefits of regular physical activity of children and potential risk from inactivity		

Course 1.3 · Recommendations for Daily Physical Activity for Children		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Focusing on the WHO recommendations for daily physical activity and quality of life in children; pyramid of physical activity and nutrition.		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Readings of evidence-based studies for benchmarks, country-specific recommendations, and country-specific reports for the achieved level of PA and quality of life in children · Approaches in evaluating daily PA level · Identification of existing policies and actions and identification of responsibilities among different stakeholders 		
Practical content	Work in small groups/focus groups discussion for preparing teaching activities that will support identified recommendations and preparing an action plan suggested to different stakeholders		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Course 1.4 · Design of Interventional Programs for Increasing Daily Physical Activity of Children in Different Settings		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Focusing on identifying possibilities for implementing physical activity for children in different settings		
	Learning the key aspects that help design successful programs and implement them in practice		
Practical content	Work in small groups for designing programs in different settings that will support children`s daily PA, and their holistic development and provide a possibility to meet WHO recommendations		
	Focus group discussion that will help teacher educators identify best practice examples, possible obstacles and how to overcome them as well as to identify ways to implement designed programs in their everyday setting		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 6 YES = minimally integrated

7 – 13 YES = partially integrated

14 – 19 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 1 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
--------	--

Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let`s look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 1	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

MODULE 2 · PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATING CHILDREN

Course 2.1 · Basic Motor Skills		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction to basic motor skills		
Practical content	Running and jumping activities		
	Throw and catch activities		
	Hand-eye coordination exercises		
	Foot-eye coordination exercises		
	Bilateral coordination exercises		
	Self-Directed Learning – Creating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Create and carry out an obstacle circuit · Throws and receptions of different heights · Patterns and movement activities 		

Course 2.2 · Collective Games and Sports		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction to collaboration		
	Introduction to team games		
Practical content	Collaboration activities		
	Group games		
	Strategy and planning activities		
	Communication and cooperation games		
	Self-Directed Learning – Creating: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Creating new activities based on what was learned · Record of successful strategies · Reports of reflection and self-assessment 		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Course 2.3 · Rhythm and Body Expression		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction to rhythm		
	Creative Movement		
	Imitation and symmetry games		
Practical content	Narration with the body Explorations of themes and characters		
	Communication and cooperation games		
	Self-Directed Learning – Creating: · Creation of own movements based on what was learned · Reflect on what they felt while moving · Create simple choreographies in groups on their own		

Course 2.4 · Psychomotor and Cognitive Development		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction to Sensory stimulation		
	Introduction to creative and logical thinking		
Practical content	Development of gross motor skills		
	Development of fine motor skills		
	Stimulation of creative thinking		
	Development of logical thinking		
	Language and communication development		
	Self-Directed Learning – Creating: · Creation of own games based on gross and fine motor skills · Reflect on what they felt executing different skills. · Record themselves doing activities that involve fine and gross motor skills		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Course 2.5 · Ethical and Social Principles in Handling Kids		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Ethical Theories and Education		
	Empathy and Equity in the Classroom		
	Children's Rights in Education		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reflective Journaling · Developing a Personal Action Plan · Continuous Self-Evaluation 		
Practical content	Conflict Resolution with Empathy		
	Inclusive Teaching Practices		
	Ethical Behavior Modeling for Educators		
	Communication and cooperation games		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 12 YES = minimally integrated

13– 24 YES = partially integrated

25 – 36 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 2 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 2	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 40 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 60 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

MODULE 3 · INCLUSIVE TEACHING

Course 3.1 · Theoretical Foundations of Inclusive Teaching		YES	NO
Theoretical content	The concept of inclusion Didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies of inclusive teaching		
	From theory to practice – inclusion in “real world” settings · Advantages and disadvantages · possible barriers in practice, “trouble shooting”		
	Self-Directed Learning – Preparing: · Preparing an inclusive teaching activity in pairs or small groups		
Course 3.2 · Inclusive Teaching in Practice		YES	NO
Practical content	Implementing the Inclusive Teaching Activities		
Course 3.3 · Reflection and Deepening of Inclusive Teaching		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Guided discussion and reflection on inclusive teaching in different settings		
	Problem-solving strategies (“trouble shooting”)		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: · Independent summary and conclusions from the discussions (pairs or small groups)		
Practical content	Group discussion on inclusion and inclusive teaching „How to teach inclusively in “my” setting/field?“		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 2 YES = minimally integrated

3 – 5 YES = partially integrated

6 – 8 YES = fully integrated

Result

My training programme has the content of Module 3

minimally

partially

fully integrated.

Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 3	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

MODULE 4 · FUNDAMENTAL MOVEMENT SKILLS & PLAY AND MOTOR SKILLSASSESSMENT

Course 4.1 · Fundamental Movement Skills and Play and their Importance for Children's Development		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Fundamental Movement Skills and Play		
	How to promote FMS and play in children? · Principles, Methods, and Resources to promote Fundamental Movement Skills and Play		
	Self-Directed Learning – Preparing: · Preparing a teaching activity		

Course 4.2 · Principles, methods, and resources to promote Fundamental Movement Skills and Play		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Deepening and interactive discussion of the principles, methods		
	Resources to promote FMS and play		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: · Reflection and evaluation of the teaching activities		
Practical content	Preparation and implementation of the teaching activities (peer teaching, pairs or small groups)		

Course 4.3 · Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Play		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Examples of motor tests, quality criteria, pedagogical aspects How to use motor tests in pedagogical settings?		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: Guided reflection and evaluation of the motor test activity, feedback to the students, using of the data		
Practical content	Preparation and implementation of motor test activities (peer teaching, pairs or small groups)		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 3 YES = minimally integrated

4 – 7 YES = partially integrated

8 – 10 YES = fully integrated

Result

My training programme has the content of Module 4

minimally

partially

fully integrated.

Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 4	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 60 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 40 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

MODULE 5 · HANDS-ON TEACHING

Course 5.1 · Fundamentals of Practical Teaching		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction to practical teaching in Early Childhood Education		
	Theories of child development and their application in the classroom Case studies: Successful teaching practices		
	Observation and documentation techniques		
	Simulations: Applying development theories in educational environments		
Practical content	Principles of inclusive education		
	Effective communication in practical teaching		
	Reflection and self-assessment of current pedagogical practices		
	Self-Directed Learning – Developing: · Developing personalized learning plans · Evaluating classroom strategies		

Course 5.2 · Practical Strategies in ECE-Settings		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Designing inclusive educational activities		
	Creating and testing educational materials		
	Developing an educational activity plan		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: · Applying tools independently · Personal development through Self-Assessment		
Practical content	Managing group dynamics and conflict resolution		
	Role-playing; classroom conflict management		
	Practical exercises in observation and documentation		
	Real-time assessment and feedback techniques		
	Reflection and self-assessment of current pedagogical practices		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Course 5.3 · Continuous Improvement and Evaluation		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Continuous improvement of pedagogical practices in early childhood education		
	Strategies for evaluating and improving pedagogical practices Case studies: Successful teaching practices		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: · Methods to actively involve parents in the educational process · Strategies to strengthen connections with the community · Examples of successful collaboration between the school, parents, and the community		
Practical content	Benefits and challenges of using technology in early childhood education		
	Useful technological tools for the early childhood classroom		
	Effective integration of technology into the educational curriculum		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 7 YES = minimally integrated 8 – 15 YES = partially integrated 16 – 23 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 5 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 5	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 60 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 40 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

MODULE 6 · PLAN, REFLECT AND LEARN

Course 6.1 · Planning and Implementing		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Planning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Why, what and when to plan? · Analysis of examples of planning in ECE · Workshop on planning in ECE settings 		
	Criteria for Implementing		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: Reading: Smith, Z., Carter, A., Fletcher, T., & Ní Chróinínd, D. (2023). What is important? How one early childhood teacher prioritised meaningful experiences for children in physical education. Journal of Early Childhood Education Research Volume 12, Issue 1,126–149		
Practical content	Practical Experience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Implement the own planning · Workshop (peer teaching) 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Portfolio: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Portfolio of own teaching experiences (peer teaching) 		

Course 6.2 · Reflecting and Evaluating from Practice		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: Reading: Villareale, C. (2009). Learning from the Children: Reflecting on Teaching. USA: Redleaf Press.		
Practical content	Strategies for observing in ECE settings		
	Analysis of observations		
	What information is valuable?		
	Analysis of peer teaching (experience)		
	Self-Directed Learning – Portfolio: Portfolio on reflecting and learning from own teaching experiences		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

Course 6.3 · Analysis Learning		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Self-review guidelines		
	Learning needs analysis: step-by-step process		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: Chan, A., & Perkins, M. (2015). Self-review processes: Using critical discourse analysis to improve practices in early childhood education settings. <i>Early Childhood Folio</i> , 19(2), 24–29. doi:10.18296/ecf.0013		
Practical content	Workshop on self-review techniques		
	Analysis of peer self-reviews		
	How to create a culture of learning in ECE context (workshop)		
	Analysis of peer teaching (experience)		
	Self-Directed Learning – Portfolio: Portfolio on reflecting and learning from own teaching experiences		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for ECE. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 6 YES = minimally integrated 7 – 13 YES = partially integrated 14 – 19 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 6 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 6	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 33,3 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 66,6 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATORS

PROGRAMME SUMMARY

Now let's take a closer look at your programme evaluation summary... and try to identify specific gaps that you might want to address:

- STEP 1** – Identify all modules where you have EduPASS content “minimally” or “partially” integrated
- STEP 2** – For those modules, count the YES and NO answers for each individual course within that module and enter those numbers in the table below
- STEP 3** – Now you'll be able to see where you have the most and least alignment of your programme compared to the proposed EduPASS content
- STEP 4** – Finally, decide if your organisational and national/regional context call for you to address this gap

	MINIMALLY INTEGRATED	PARTIALLY INTEGRATED	FULLY INTEGRATED	GAP SHOULD BE ADDRESSED
Module 1 · Daily Physical Activity and Play				YES / NO
Course 1.1 · Child Holistic Development				
Course 1.2 · Importance of Physical Activity and Play for Children's Holistic Development and overall Well-being				
Course 1.3 · Recommendations for Daily Physical Activity for Children				
Course 1.4 · Design of Intervention Programmes for Increasing Daily Physical Activity of Children in Different Settings				
Module 2 · Principles of Educating Children				YES / NO
Course 2.1 · Basic Motor Skills				
Course 2.2 · Collective Games and Sports				
Course 2.3 · Rhythm and Body Expression				
Course 2.4 · Psychomotor and Cognitive Development				
Course 2.5 · Ethical and Social Principles in Handling Kids				
Module 3 · Inclusive Teaching				YES / NO
Course 3.1 · Theoretical Foundations of Inclusive Teaching				
Course 3.2 · Inclusive Teaching in Practice				
Course 3.3 · Reflection and Deepening of Inclusive Teaching				
Module 4 · Fundamental Movement Skills & Play and Motor Skills Assessment				YES / NO
Course 4.1 · Fundamental Movement Skills and Play and their Importance for Children's Development				
Course 4.2 · Principles, methods, and resources to promote Fundamental Movement Skills and Play				
Course 4.3 · Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Play				
Module 5 · Hands-on Teaching				YES / NO
Course 5.1 · Fundamentals of Practical Teaching				
Course 5.2 · Practical Strategies in ECE-Settings				
Course 5.3 · Continuous Improvement and Evaluation				
Module 6 · Plan, Reflect and Learn				YES / NO
Course 6.1 · Planning and Implementing				
Course 6.2 · Reflecting and Evaluating from Practice				
Course 6.3 · Analysis Learning				

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 1 · DAILY PHYSICAL ACTIVITY & SPORT AND MOTOR SKILLS ASSESSMENT

Course 1.1 · Needs and Benefits of Daily Physical Activities		YES	NO
Theoretical content	The needs and benefits of daily PA from physical, psychosocial and mental perspective		
	WHO, EU and national guidelines		
	Physical literacy and its domains – Think, Feel and Do		
	Concept of holistic development (Physical literacy) · Specifics of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development of 5 – 12 year old children · The importance of an holistic approach from the aspect of physical activity		
	Self-Directed Learning – Independent project: For a target age group, identify the benefits of PA for children, the types of PA that suit children and the approach to be taken in the development of motor, cognitive, and socio-emotional development of children		

Course 1.2 · Monitoring and Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills (FMS) and Sport Skills (SK)		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Field tests of FMS and SK development		
	Tests for cognitive and affective domains of PL		
	Monitoring criteria and applications for measurement		
	Peer application and analysis of results (develop ability to conducted each test reliably)		
	Collection of assessment criteria and cut off points to evaluate children		
	Adolescents at risk and in healthy developmental zones for FMS and SK / cognitive and affective domains of PL		
	Self-Directed Learning – Application: · Application with children and analysis of results · Age-related tool kits for measurement in the gym and on the pitch		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 1.3 · Applying toolkits and test items for measurement and assessment		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Transfer of Knowledge into Practice: · What we learned and how to apply our knowledge in the gym/on the pitch for measurement and assessments		
	· Planning for visit to schools / clubs		
	· Organization of testing equipment		
	· Timetable for explanation to children, data collection, analysis of results and presentation back to children		
Practical content	Applying the tests with Children from data collection to preparation of reports of results)		
	Prepare a stationary of measurement, prepare each station of the test and conduct measurement of the item of the test battery		
	analysis and evaluation of the collected data compared to given age-related cut off points/healthy zones of measurement results		
	Self-Directed Learning – Preparation: · Presentation of results and implications for each child · Documentation of individual measurement result · Student-centered protocols · Formats for feedback reports		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 6 YES = minimally integrated 7 – 13 YES = partially integrated 14 – 20 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 1 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 1	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 60 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 40 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 2 · PRINCIPLES OF COACHING CHILDREN

Course 2.1 · ICOACHKIDS Pledge – 10 Principles of Coaching Children		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Child-centred sport, addressing the needs of the whole child, including all children and engaging parents		
	Setting an environment that is fun and safe for children and focusses on each child developing a love of being active		
	Foundational skills for children – cognitive, affective and psychomotor		
	Progressive programmes and different learning methods		
	Using competition in a developmental way		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Developing Effective Environments For Youth Sport, Chapter 1: The Role of the Children’s Coach, Section3, page 33-38 · Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf 		
Practical content	Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Each student should explain which key principles are applied in their session. · The evaluation should affirm if the principles were applied, and what else could be done to further include the principles. 		

Course 2.2 · Child Development and Implications for Physical Activity		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Understanding Physical Literacy: Definition of Physical Literacy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The domains of physical literacy – cognitive, affective and psychomotor 		
	The individual’s physical literacy journey – How and where children can develop physical literacy		
	Using physical literacy as a lens when coaching children		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Study guide for ICK MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy, Chapter 3: How Children Grow and Develop - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf) 		
Practical content	Child Development – Social, Physical, Emotional and Cognitive (SPEC) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The social development of children – learning to act with others and the world around them 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The physical development of children – general growth, chronical age, biological age (puberty and growth spurt) 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The emotional development of children – awareness of self (feelings), talking about emotions (language and vocabulary), understanding / controlling emotions, empathy, dealing with authority / conflict 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The cognitive development of children – thinking, problem solving, forming judgements, decision making and learning 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Creating a developmental climate – role model, interaction, learning activities to suit individuals, coaching tools – question, listening, self-referenced (ipsative) Feedback 		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 2.3 · Motivating Children in Sport		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Understanding the Psycho-Social Development of Children <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The development of Self · Emotional, social, cognitive and moral development 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Life skills development 		
	Motivating Children in Sport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Self-determination – competence, autonomy and belonging · Achievement goals – mastery orientation and performance orientation · The coach-athlete relationship 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complete MOOC 1, Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport, Chapter 4: Chapter-4-What-sport-means-for-children-and-what-it-can-do-for-their-personal-development-Study-Guide.pdf · Complete MOOC 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy, Chapter 1: Motivating Children in Sport: Chapter-1-Motivation-in-Sport-Study-Guide.pdf 		

Course 2.4 · Setting a Caring Environment		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Creating a Caring Climate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Identify what is a caring climate · Building effective relationships with children and parents · Being an inclusive coach 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 1, Chapter 5, Developing Effective Environments for Youth Sport, Chapter 5: Creating a Pedagogical Climate 		
Practical content	Practically Setting up a Caring Climate Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students. Each student should explain how a caring climate is applied in their session. The evaluation should affirm if the caring climate was applied and how, and what else could be done to further develop the caring climate.		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 2.5 · Safe Sport Climate for Children		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Creating a Safe Sport Climate · Define a Safe Sport Climate – where children feel safe to learn, have opportunities to learn and improve and where children feel the coach cares for them		
	Developing a Child-Centred Coaching Philosophy		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: · Complete the study guide for ICK MOOC 1, Chapter 2, What-is-a-coaching-philosophy-and-why-it-is-beneficial-to-be-clear-about-yours-Study-Guide.pdf		
Practical content	Peer-coaching sessions that are planned, delivered and evaluated by the students · Each student should explain how a safe sport climate is applied in their session. · The evaluation should affirm if the safe sport climate was applied and how, and what else could be done to further develop the safe sport climate		
	Using your coaching tools to reflect a coaching philosophy – how you communicate and what you do in coaching session and at competition		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 10 YES = minimally integrated 11 – 21 YES = partially integrated 22 – 32 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 2 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 2	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 66,6 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 33,3 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 3 · INCLUSIVE COACHING / SAFEGUARDING

Course 3.1 · Exploring Inclusiveness in Sport		YES	NO
Theoretical content	<p>Inclusion and the different dimensions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Classification and differentiation between inclusion and integration · PAMPS is there for all children · Inclusion Spectrum Model and the STEP Model for classifying and planning sports programmes to support and challenge each child individually 		
	<p>'Be inclusive'</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · The importance of the youth sports coach's own behaviour · What is meant by inclusive behaviour? What values are represented and how does inclusive language and communication work? How can I behave inclusively? 		
	<p>Self-Directed Learning – Readings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · https://icoachkids.org/learn/inclusion/the-inclusion-spectrum · https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/i-coach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-chapter-2-190621110212.pdf 		
Practical content	<p>Practical application and testing of the inclusion model for planning and implementing PAMPS programmes. Experience differentiation for the different starting points of the children through the STEP model</p>		
	<p>Practical application and testing of inclusive behaviour (language, positioning, choice of movement task and differentiation options for all children) through the teaching of sports programmes (PAMPS) and subsequent reflection on them</p>		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 3.2 · Effective Relationships		YES	NO
Theoretical content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Importance of the coach-child relationship · basic needs for potential development – Self-Determination-Theory (SDT) (Deci & Ryan) · Why children choose a sport and stick with it? Why children stop playing sport and what you can do about it? · 3+1C Model (Jowett, 2017) 		
	Role of the parents in youth sport <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · How do you create a parent-friendly environment? How do you involve parents positively? 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Chapter 1: https://inclusiveskating.org/resources/icoach-kids-study-guide-mooc-2-introduction-190621110025.pdf · https://icoachkids.org/learn/parents/working-with-parents-in-sport 		
Practical content	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Role play – Develop and play out a parent-coach meeting 		
	Practical application and testing of the 3+1C model in the implementation of and interaction with children and subsequent reflection on it		

Course 3.3 · Adapting your Programme – Coaching Girls in Sport		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introduction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Dropout And Engagement in Girls’ Sport and Physical Activity · Meeting the Psycho-Social Needs of Girls in Sport 		
	Group Discussion: Coach-Athlete Relationship in Girls’ Sport		
	Body Image and Maturation		
	The Girls in Sport Elements: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Focus on competence 2. Provide non-competitive activities 3. Provide high support 4. Offer a variety of activities and variations 5. Use role models 6. Promote friendships and social connections 7. Help coaches to understand girls’ needs 8. Create a positive, inclusive and welcoming environment 9. Provide girls only opportunities 10. Mitigate issues related to body image and act accordingly 		
Practical content	Self-Directed Learning – Reading: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · https://icoachkids.org/learn/coaching-girls/icoachgirls/guide1 		
	Practical application and creating a positive mastery motivational climate for girls and subsequent reflection on it		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 3.4 · Safeguarding – Basics of Safe Environments		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Staying Safe as a Coach · Safeguarding and Child Protection		
	· Preventing and Taking Action against Child Abuse in Sport		
	Role of the parents in youth sport · How do you create a parent-friendly environment? How do you involve parents positively?		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: · https://www.unicef.org.uk/sport-for-development/safeguarding-in-sport/ · International Safeguarding for Children in Sport		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 8 YES = minimally integrated 9 – 17 YES = partially integrated 18 – 26 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 3 <input type="checkbox"/> minimally <input type="checkbox"/> partially <input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 3	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 70 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 30 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 4 · FUNDAMENTAL MOVEMENT SKILLS AND PLAY

Course 4.1 · Understanding Motor Skill Development		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Mental Practice and Automatic stages of skill development		
	Blocked, Variable and Random practice (short-term learning); and Deliberate practice and play (long-term learning)		
	Short-term learning activities - Rapid Improvement, Not mentally demanding, Helpful for beginners / young, Confidence builder, Low retention / transfer, Quickly becomes boring and mindless		
	Long-Term Learning Practice - Promote player's own thinking, Encourages retrieval of previous learning in a dynamic / realistic environment, High retention / transfer, Develops adaptable skills, Slow improvement, Mentally demanding / draining		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complete the activities in MOOC 2, Chapter 4 – Motor Skills Development and Conditioning for Children COURSE 2: Child-Centred Coaching and Physical Literacy (icoachkids.org) 		
Practical content	Types of Practice leading to short-term and long-term learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Practical application stages of skill development and types of practice 		
	Use of coaching skills of planning, organisation, explanation, demonstration and safe practice		

Course 4.2 · Developing Balance, Coordination, Agility and Speed		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Understanding Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Balance · Coordination · Agility and Speed 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention in a child's competence for each of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed. · Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of each of balance, coordination and agility and speed. As an example use the resource – Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet 		
Practical content	Practical application in the development of Balance, Coordination and Agility and Speed		
	Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning		
	Focus on all coaching skills, with an emphasis on observation analysis and the identification of point of improvement		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 4.3 · Developing Fundamental Motor Skills		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Fundamental Motor Skills – Stability, Locomotion and Object Control <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Stability · Locomotion · Object Control 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement and intervention (specifically ipsative feedback) in a child's competence for each of a fundamental motor skill linked to Stability, Locomotion and Object Control. · Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of each of Stability, Locomotion and Object Control. As an example use the resource - Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet 		
Practical content	Practical application in the development of a range of fundamental motor skills, using the categories of Stability, Locomotion and Object Control		
	Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning.		
	Focus on all coaching skills, emphasising observation analysis, the identification of point of improvement, and providing ipsative feedback		

Course 4.4 · Developing Game Skills and Play		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Games Skills and Play <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Games skills · Play / Deliberate Practice / Play · Game Design 		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Case studies on the observation, analysis, identify points of improvement, intervention and questioning and listening in a child's competence for game skills through play, and in game design. · Development of a bank of activities for the Youth Sports Coach to use in the development of game skills through play and in game design. As an example use the resource - Move Well, Move Often - Physical Literacy - Scoilnet 		
Practical content	Practical application in the development of a range of game skills, using play and deliberate play.		
	Use different types of activities for short/long term development and learning.		
	Focus on all coaching skills, emphasising observation analysis, the identification of point of improvement, and providing ipsative feedback and an emphasis on questioning, listening and the voice of the child, including them in game skill development and game design		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 9 YES = minimally integrated 10 – 19 YES = partially integrated 20 – 28 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 4	<input type="checkbox"/> minimally	<input type="checkbox"/> partially	<input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 4	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 50 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 5 · HANDS-ON COACHING

Course 5.1 · Fundamentals to Coaching Practice		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Introducing the Youth Sport Compass model: development-oriented, motivational, socially-safe, and caring coaching		
	Children are not mini-adults: make sport fit the child, not the child fit the sport		
	SPEC model (Lara-Bercial, 2012): non-linear development along cognitive, social, physical, emotional, and biological, impacted by chronological, biological, and training ages		
	Coaching Zones: Boredom, Comfort, Learning and Panic zones		
	The Multi-Skills Jigsaw (Lara-Bercial et al., 2015)		
	What do children want from a coach		
	Building relationships		
	Identifying differences and different needs in children/learners		
	Motivation: What do children want from sport (it's NOT competing all the time...)		
	Building Blocks towards a motivated and confident child in sport		
	The Coach's Toolkit: Explanations, Demonstrations, Setting up and Standing back, Questioning and Listening, Feedback and Reflection		
Practical content	<p>Self-Directed Learning – Reflection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Watch Youth Sport Compass video and reflect on how it relates to your current coaching experience https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83McfP3FUOk · Reflect on how the SPEC model relates to your current coaching practice: How are you considering and supporting cognitive, social, physical, and emotional development · Watch the Coach's Toolkit videos on the ICOACHKIDS website. Then download the handouts and reflect on how well your coaching practice currently aligns with these recommendation · Complete the ICOACHKIDS Course 3 "Coaching on the Ground: Planning, Doing and Reviewing" and complete the Study Guides 		
	Small group discussion: how is each of you creating a positive environment where children can thrive by using the Youth Sport Compass model? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them?		
	Small group discussion: how does the SPEC model relate to your current coaching practice and how are you considering and supporting cognitive, social, physical, and emotional development? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them?		
	Group discussion: Understanding the wants and needs of children is essential to any coach. These wants and needs are factors that underpin successful learning. How do you identify wants and needs of the children you coach? What gaps have you identified, and how will you be able to address them?		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 5.2 · Preparing Hands-on Coaching Practice		YES	NO
Theoretical content	<p>Self-Directed Learning – My Coaching Session Planner:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Read, watch and reflect on the information about the Lifelong Learning Coach on the ICOACHKIDS website 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Engage with the issue-specific Online Tool to create a specific image and affirmations that will ground and guide you during your coaching session, supporting your coaching philosophy 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complete the Coaching Session Planner 1 to specifically map out your coaching session 		
Practical content	<p>Complete and discuss “What are You Bringing to Your Coaching” worksheet (Values/Beliefs, Sport Experiences, Education, Life Experience/Learning, Other things... What does each of those experiences bring to your coaching?)</p>		
	<p>Complete and discuss “Coaches Learn Best” worksheet</p>		
	<p>Revisit/revise/create your coaching philosophy: A coaching philosophy provides a set of explicit guidelines on how to translate your core values and beliefs into actions. As such, it is inherently practical: it allows you to plan, deliver and reflect more effectively. The Youth Sport Compass and ICoachKids Pledge offer foundations for a sound coaching philosophy.</p>		
	<p>Engaging with the Coach Toolkit framework for session preparation: What are your learning intentions? What activities will you implement to achieve those outcomes? How will you use Progressive Game Builds and Recycling? How are you implementing the Voice of the Child? How will you Explain, Demonstrate, Set up, Stand back, Question and Listen, provide Feedback, Reflect (during the session)?</p>		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 5.3 · Hands-on Coaching Experience & Debrief		YES	NO
Theoretical content	<p>Self-Directed Learning – Reflections: Engage in specific reflection “on practice”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · How did your coaching philosophy help you? · How did you hear “The Voice of the Child”? · What did you apply and what worked from the Youth Sport Compass climate model? · Which Coach’s Toolkit parts did 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · What are Personal Learnings from the hands-on coaching experience? 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · What are Personal Improvement Goals after your hands-on coaching experience? 		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Watch the ICOACHKIDS video on “Behavior Change Tips for Coaches” Explore the ICOACHKIDS “Your Learning as a Coach” resources 		
Practical content	<p>Set-up and do your hands-on coaching session 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Debrief your session1 group · Personal reflection on hands-on coaching session 1 		
	<p>Set-up and do your hands-on coaching session 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Debrief your session2 group · Personal reflection on hands-on coaching session 2 		
	<p>Debrief of hands-on coaching session 1 (and session 2, subsequently): use reflection models like “two stars (positives), one wish (growth spot)” or the KISS model (Keep, Increase, Stop, Start)</p>		
	<p>Discuss self-reflection and observer feedback on session 1 (and session 2, subsequently)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Where does it align, differ? 		
	<p>What are specific improvement goals for session 2?</p>		
	<p>Complete the Coaching Session Planner 2 to specifically map out your coaching session for amended peer-coaching session</p>		
	<p>Self-Directed Learning – Coaching Work-Placement Programme: Engage in 10 coaching sessions with 2 hrs each to plan, deliver, and reflect as part of a Coaching Work-Placement programme. Maintain a Coaching Diary to track planning, organisation, delivery, reflection, and learning on each coaching session; add reflections on overall placement and overall learnings</p>		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 11 YES = minimally integrated

12 – 22 YES = partially integrated

23 – 33 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 5	<input type="checkbox"/> minimally	<input type="checkbox"/> partially	<input type="checkbox"/> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 5	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 45 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 55 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

MODULE 6 · PLAN, REFLECT AND LEARN

Course 6.1 · Child-Centred Planning for Clubs / Schools and alignment of Personal Coaching Philosophy		YES	NO
Theoretical content	The Coach Decision Making Model (ESCF, 2017 - CoachLearn European Sport Coaching Framework)		
	Personal Coaching Philosophy, its development and growth		
	A child-centred vision and strategy for a club / school		
	Planning, doing and reviewing on the ground		
	Self-Directed Learning – Readings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · MOOC 1, Chapter 1, Section 2: Children Sport – Reality Check - Chapter-1-The-Role-of-the-Childrens-Sport-Coach-Study-Guide.pdf · MOOC 1, Chapter 2: Chapter-2-What-is-a-coaching-philosophy-and-why-it-is-beneficial-to-be-clear-about-yours-Study-Guide.pdf · MOOC 1, Chapter 3: Creating A vision and Strategy for Your Club - Chapter-3-How-to-create-a-suitable-vision-for-your-team-or-your-club-Study-Guide.pdf 		
Practical content	Alignment of coaching philosophy and coaching behaviours The clubs/ schools policy and values and your personal coaching philosophy in practice(practice of coaching and review of coaching behaviours) – are they aligned?		

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

Course 6.2 · Reflection and Learning		YES	NO
Theoretical content	Reflection during practice and Reflection on practice		
	Use of technology (video)		
	Reflection with co-coaches, with a partner and as part of a group		
	Learning with a mentor		
	Setting personal improvement goals		
	Self-Directed Learning – Reflection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Complete a personal reflection journal, using a variety of reflection methods (individual, group, mentor, video); and write up a personal case study to include: · Review club values and policy · Create personal coaching philosophy · Evaluate coaching behaviours and alignment with philosophy · Journal reflection and change of coaching behaviour over time · Document changes and grow of your personal coaching philosophy · Continuously set personal improvement goals 		
Practical content	Practical application and development of reflection skills		
	Awareness of your coaching skills and behaviours; and setting of personal improvement goals		
	Your personal coaching philosophy in practice – practice of coaching and review of coaching behaviours – are they aligned?		

You have answered all the questions with YES or NO and assessed, which content of the respective EduPASS module is already integrated into your training or further education programme for YSC. Now, count your YES answers and see to what extent the EduPASS contents are already integrated.

Rating scale

0 – 5 YES = minimally integrated 6 – 10 YES = partially integrated 11 – 15 YES = fully integrated

Result	My training programme has the content of Module 6 <div style="display: inline-block; width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #ccc; margin: 0 5px;"></div> minimally <div style="display: inline-block; width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #ccc; margin: 0 5px;"></div> partially <div style="display: inline-block; width: 15px; height: 15px; background-color: #ccc; margin: 0 5px;"></div> fully integrated.
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Between theory and practice

To gauge the distribution of theory and practice in this specific module, let's look at your own training programme and check how you are currently distributing theoretical and practical content. For the respective EduPASS module, an approximate estimate of the distribution between theory and practice in percent is presented in brackets below.

Theory and Practice for Module 6	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90 %	100 %
Theoretical training in this subject area (~ 66,6 %)											
Practical training in this subject area (~ 33,3 %)											

SELF-CHECK TOOL FOR YOUTH SPORT COACHES

PROGRAMME SUMMARY

Now let's take a closer look at your programme evaluation summary... and try to identify specific gaps that you might want to address:

- STEP 1** – Identify all modules where you have EduPASS content “minimally” or “partially” integrated
- STEP 2** – For those modules, count the YES and NO answers for each individual course within that module and enter those numbers in the table below
- STEP 3** – Now you'll be able to see where you have the most and least alignment of your programme compared to the proposed EduPASS content
- STEP 4** – Finally, decide if your organisational and national/regional context call for you to address this gap

	MINIMALLY INTEGRATED	PARTIALLY INTEGRATED	FULLY INTEGRATED	GAP SHOULD BE ADDRESSED
Module 1 · Daily Physical Activity and Sport & Motor Skills Assessment				YES / NO
Course 1.1 · Needs & benefits of daily physical activities				
Course 1.2 · Monitoring and Assessment of Fundamental Movement Skills and Sport Skills (SK)				
Course 1.3 · Applying toolkits and test items for measurement and assessment				
Module 2 · Principles of Coaching Children				YES / NO
Course 2.1 · ICOACHKIDS Pledge – 10 Principles of Coaching Children				
Course 2.2 · Child Development and Implications for Physical Activity				
Course 2.3 · Motivating Children in Sport				
Course 2.4 · Setting a Caring Environment				
Course 2.5 · Safe Sport Climate for Children				
Module 3 · Inclusive Coaching / Safeguarding				YES / NO
Course 3.1 · Exploring Inclusiveness in Sport				
Course 3.2 · Effective Relationships				
Course 3.3 · Adapting your Programme – Coaching Girls in Sport				
Course 3.4 · Safeguarding – Basics of Safe Environments				
Module 4 · Fundamental Movement Skills and Play				YES / NO
Course 4.1 · Understanding Motor Skill Development				
Course 4.2 · Developing Balance, Coordination, Agility and Speed				
Course 4.3 · Developing Fundamental Motor Skills				
Course 4.4 · Developing Game Skills and Play				
Module 5 · Hands-on Coaching				YES / NO
Course 5.1 · Fundamentals of Coaching Practice				
Course 5.2 · Preparing Hands-on Coaching Practice				
Course 5.3 · Hands-on Coaching Experience & Debrief				
Module 6 · Plan, Reflect and Learn				YES / NO
Course 6.1 · Child-Centred Planning for Clubs / Schools and alignment of Personal Coaching Philosophy				
Course 6.2 · Reflection and Learning				